

Iodometric Determination of Certain Organic Acids

S. N. NEMA, G. P. SONI and R. M. VERMA*

Department of Post-Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of Jabalpur, Jabalpur

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AN iodometric determination of carboxyl group in certain organic acids at room temperature has been described.

The well-known analytical reaction between iodide and iodate in presence of acid solution

has been used for the determination of acids; this is used as an alternative, often more accurate to the usual titration with alkali¹. Iodide present is oxidized, in amounts equivalent to the acid present, to iodine which is titrated with thiosulphate. The position of the equilibrium of the reaction is strongly influenced by the pH of the solution. The iodometric method gives excellent result even with dilute solutions of strong acids provided the iodide-iodate mixture is allowed to stand for at least 15 minutes before titration². This method, however, fails in case of weak acids when the pH at the end-point is too high to effect complete reaction^{2,3}. Bruhns⁴ achieved quantitative reaction in about half an hour by adding calcium or magnesium chloride to the reaction mixture. But this procedure is applicable only to organic hydroxy acids. Another modification due to Kolthoff⁵ involves the addition of a measured excess of thiosulphate to acid solution containing iodide and iodate and subsequent titration of the residual thiosulphate with iodine. With dilute solutions the reaction is much slower making the reaction unsuitable for use in the quantitative analysis of weak acids. This modification has been adopted for estimating the acid content in various products; the time allowed for the reaction being 2-24 hours⁷⁻⁹. These procedures require much time moreover, there is a possibility of thiosulphate reacting with acid. The reaction time cannot be shortened by heating due to volatility of iodine. In order to speed up the iodometric determination of weak acids, the reaction between certain organic acids, iodide and iodate was studied from analytical view point and the following inferences were drawn.

(a) In a set of experiments, the volume of iodide and iodate solution was increased stepwise. But even a large excess of iodate and iodide solution could not make the reaction quantitative in 15-30 minutes at room temperature. The slow reaction rate is due to increase in the overall volume of the reaction mixture as iodide and iodate solutions are

added. This view was supported by a study on the dilution effect which revealed that there is a sharp fall in the reaction velocity with increase in the volume of the reaction mixture. It follows that the reaction rate can be accelerated by keeping the volume of the reaction mixture at a minimum.

(b) In view of the above observation, the addition of suitable amounts of iodide and iodate in the solid form was attempted which made the reaction to go to completion in 2-10 minutes at room temperature. The reaction time could be extended up to 30-60 minutes with no adverse effects. Likewise, the addition of even undue large excess of solid iodide and iodate did not interfere with the results.

On the basis of the afore-mentioned observations, a procedure has been evolved for the iodometric determination of sixteen aliphatic acids.

Experimental

The following solutions were prepared using Chemicals of A. R. grade.

0.1N solutions of different acids were prepared by standardization with alkali. 0.05, 0.025, 0.01 and 0.005N solutions were then prepared by suitably diluting 0.1N solution.

0.1N thiosulphate was prepared and standardized with standard iodate. 0.05, 0.025, 0.01 and 0.005N solutions were prepared by diluting with conductivity water.

Recommended Procedure :

5-20 ml of the acid sample containing 0.05-0.5 meq. of carboxyl group is pipetted into a 100 ml iodine flask. 1-5 g of solid potassium iodide and 1-3 g of solid potassium iodate are added and the contents of the flask are stirred using a magnetic stirrer. After waiting for 2-10 minutes the liberated iodine is titrated with thiosulphate solution (0.05-0.005N) through a microburette using starch as indicator.

1 ml of 0.01N thiosulphate \equiv 0.45 mg of carboxyl group.

Results and Discussion

In titrating a dilute solution of a weak acid with 0.01N sodium hydroxide solution, the recognition of the end-point is not easy because the phenolphthalein colour fades rapidly¹⁰. This difficulty increases with increasing dilution of the titrant solution. In the proposed iodometric method there is not much difficulty in detecting the end-point when 0.005N or even more dilute solution of thiosulphate

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

is used as the titrant. Furthermore, while determining the acid content of a product containing a component capable of reacting with alkali, the titration with alkali cannot yield correct results. For example, in estimating carboxy acids in lac, the resin present undergoes saponification⁶. In certain products which are slightly coloured the neutralization indicators may not be very suitable. For these reasons attempts were made^{4,5} to evolve an iodometric method for the estimation of weak acids—but these attempts had limited applicability and were time consuming. Kolthoff's modified procedure⁵ has been adopted by several workers⁷⁻⁹ for estimating the acid content in a number of products, but the time required for the completion of the reaction is 2-24 hours. The proposed procedure is simple, rapid and accurate; being iodometric it possesses sharp end-point, the amounts of reagent and reaction time are not critical and hence it can be adopted with advantage for the titrimetric determination of dilute solutions of weak acids.

TABLE 1—IODOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CERTAIN ORGANIC ACIDS
(Room Temperature 30-35°)

Sl. No.	Acids	KIO, KI added		Reaction time (mins)	% Deviation*	
		(g)	(g)		Proposed method	Comparison method**
1.	Formic	1	2	2	0.1	0.5
2.	Acetic	2	2	5	0.2	0.6
3.	Monochloroacetic	0.5	0.5	2	0.2	0.6
4.	Dichloroacetic	0.5	0.5	2	0.1	0.5
5.	Trichloroacetic	0.5	0.5	2	0.2	0.7
6.	Propionic	2	5	5	0.4	0.9
7.	β -chloropropionic	1	2	2	0.3	0.8
8.	Butyric	2	5	5	0.5	0.9
9.	Oxalic	1	1	2	0.2	0.6
10.	Malonic	2	5	10	0.3	0.7
11.	Succinic	2	5	10	0.5	0.9
12.	Glycollic	1	2	5	0.2	0.8
13.	Malic	1	1	2	0.2	0.7
14.	Tartaric	1	1	2	0.4	0.6
15.	Citric	1	1	5	0.3	0.7
16.	Crotonic	1	2	5	0.2	0.6

* Average of six determinations.

** In these titrations phenolphthalein colour faded rapidly. The first appearance of red colour was taken as the end-point.

In case of acids 3, 4 and 5 iodide and iodate solutions can also be employed. In case of acid 10, the reaction-time should not exceed 15 mins otherwise low results are obtained.

Table 1 shows the amount of potassium iodide and potassium iodate to be added and reaction time to be allowed in case of sixteen acids examined. A comparative study of determination of these acids at micro level (0.05 meq. of acid present in 10 ml of assay solution) by iodometry and alkalimetry has also been presented in this table. The concentration of the titrant solution (sodium thiosulphate or sodium hydroxide) used was 0.005N.

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Polarographic Study of Ni(II)-Succinimide System

(KM.) KRISHNA,* (KM.) ANJU VARSHNEY

and

M. C. DUBEY

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra, India

and

S. K. JHA

Institute de Quimica, Universidade Federal da Bahia, Salvador, Bahia, Brazil

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A survey of the literature reveals that although the behaviour of Ni(II) in presence of various complexing media has been investigated but very few studies have been reported with amides^{1,2}. Ni(II)-succinimide system has not been investigated so far. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to study the polarographic behaviour of Ni(II) in the presence of succinimide.

Experimental

Ni(NO₃)₂.6H₂O was used as the source for depolarizer metal ion, Ni(II). Supporting electrolyte was KCl. The potassium salt of succinimide was prepared from succinimide and KOH. All the chemicals used were of high purity (B.D.H or S. Merck) and all the solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. In the final polarographic

* To whom all correspondence should be directed.